

Machine Learning Models for Cardiovascular Disease Events Prediction*

Konstantina Tsarapatsani, Antonis I. Sakellarios, Vasileios C. Pezoulas, Vassilis D. Tsakanikas, Marcus E. Kleber, Winfried März, Lampros K. Michalis, and Dimitrios I. Fotiadis, *Fellow member*,
IEEE

Abstract—Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are among the most serious disorders leading to high mortality rates worldwide. CVDs can be diagnosed and prevented early by identifying risk biomarkers using statistical and machine learning (ML) models. Researchers use these models to analyze medical data, assisting in disease prediction. In this work, we utilize clinical CVD risk factors and molecular data using machine learning models such as Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine, Naïve Bayes, Extreme Grading Boosting and Adaptive Boosting to predict after ten years death caused by CVD. We used the cohort of the Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) study, in which 2943 patients included in the analysis (484 annotated as dead due to CVD). We calculate the Accuracy (ACC), Precision, Recall, F1-Score, Specificity (SPE) and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) of each model. The findings of the comparative analysis show that machine learning algorithm, Logistic Regression, has been proven to be the most accurate and reliable algorithm with a presented accuracy 72.20 %.

Keywords—Machine Learning Models, Cardiovascular Disease, Risk Scores, 10-Year Risk of CVD.

I. INTRODUCTION

CVD is a main disorder for humans, accounting for approximately 17.9 million deaths every year worldwide, which represents 32% of all global deaths [1]. CVD is expected to account for >23.6 million deaths annually by 2030 [2]. In Europe, there were 1.68 million deaths resulting from cardiovascular disease in 2016, which was equivalent to 37.1 % of all deaths [3]. Several risk factors can trigger cardiovascular disease, such as diabetes mellitus, LDL cholesterol, blood pressure, irregular pulse rate, physical activity, unhealthy diet, family history of CVD and ethnic background. Cardiovascular disease can be predicted using multiple tests. However, the lack of expertise of medical staff can make early diagnosis difficult [4]. It is necessary to evaluate the risk of cardiovascular disease for prevention, primary and secondary. There are several statistical risk scores that predict the risk of patients with previous CVD event or

non-CVD event, including SCORE2 (Systematic COronary Risk Evaluation 2) [5], QRISK3 [6], Framingham Risk Score (FRS) [7], Joint British Society risk calculator 3 (JBS3) [8], Atherosclerotic Cardiovascular Disease (ASCVD) [9], American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association (ACC/AHA) [9], HeartScore [10], WHO risk score [11], and CoroPredict [12].

The effectiveness of the statistical models, risk scores, was evaluated in several studies [13-14] based on different ethnicities. The main outcome of these works was that these scores predict the percentage of patients to be at high or low risk of developing CVD. Machine learning algorithm is an alternative effective approach, which can also be used for the detection of disease outcomes and events, when trained on proper medical data. Recently, the machine learning models were used extensively for the prediction of CVD [15-17]. The proposed machine learning models achieve good predictions of CVD, with accuracy larger than 90%. More specifically, in [18], the hyOPTXg model extracted the highest AUC value equal to 0.947, with the use of optimization techniques (min-max scaling, OPTUNA: Hyper-parameter tuning) and an optimized Extreme Gradient Booster. In another study [19], in which ten ML models were applied, the Extreme Gradient Boost and Gradient Boost presented the highest AUC value (0.812). Also, compared to Framingham and ACC/AHA risk models, the ML models presented equal to or greater outcomes.

In addition, Pouriyeh *et al.* [20], used different machine learning approaches including Naive Bayes (NB), Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), Decision Tree (DT), K-Nearest Neighbor (K-NN), Radial Basis Function (RBF), Support Vector Machine (SVM) and Single Conjunctive Rule Learner (SCRL), on the Cleveland Heart Disease database. They applied the bagging, boosting and stacking, in order to evaluate the performance of each classifier and such classifiers in combination. The comparison of all classifiers shows that SVM achieved the highest accuracy and SCRL has the lowest accuracy with 84.15% and 69.96%, respectively. Furthermore,

* This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017424, as part of TIMELY project.

D. I. Fotiadis, V. C. Pezoulas, V. D. Tsakanikas and A. I. Sakellarios are with the Unit of Medical Technology and Intelligent Information Systems, Dept. of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Ioannina, GR 45110, Ioannina, Greece, and with the Biomedical Institute, Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas (FORTH) (phone: +30 26510 09006; fax: +302651005588; emails: fotiadis@uoi.gr, bpezoulas@gmail.com, Vasilistsakanikas@gmail.com, ansakel@cc.uoi.gr).

K. Tsarapatsani is with the Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Foundation for Research and Technology-Hellas (FORTH) (email: k.tsarapatsani@gmail.com)

L. K. Michalis is with the Michaelideion Cardiac Center, Dept. of Cardiology, Medical School, University of Ioannina, GR 45110 Ioannina, Greece (email: lmihalidis@cc.uoi.gr).

M. E. Kleber with Medical Clinic V, Mannheim Medical Faculty, University of Heidelberg, Mannheim, Germany (email: marcus.kleber@medma.uni-heidelberg.de).

W. März is with Mannheim Institute of Public Health, Social and Preventive Medicine, Medical Faculty Mannheim, University of Heidelberg, Mannheim, Germany (email: winfried.maerz@synlab.com).

SVM is still the best approach with the same accuracy percentage, whenever the bagging method is applied. However, in this case, DT is the worst model with 78.54%. SVM has also improved to 84.81% with the use of bagging. The combination of classifiers, MLP and SVM, proved to be the most accurate with 84.15%, after the stacking.

Our goal is the prediction of death caused by CVD after ten years of follow-up using only simple biomarkers which are routinely collected in the Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) dataset [21]. In particular, we applied six different machine learning algorithms from which the best performance is presented by Logistic Regression. The results shows that the mean values of accuracy and area under receiver operative characteristic curve 72.20 % and 72.97 %, respectively.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Overall workflow

Fig. 1 depicts the workflow of this analysis. We started with LURIC dataset, which includes patients scheduled for coronary angiography. This was followed by preprocessing the data with cleaning and feature selection techniques. Subsequently we utilized ML algorithms and Class Imbalance handling. As a result of that, we calculated the performance of ML algorithms in predicting death by CVD. These results are part of the TIMELY study that aims to estimate the risk score and mortality of CVD in patients with 10-year risk.

Figure 1. Working diagram of current study.

B. Data description

In this study, the medical data used were from the Ludwigshafen Risk and Cardiovascular Health (LURIC) cohort [21]. It contains 3,316 patients and 3,023 features including demographics, daily habits, biomarkers, such as inflammatory and molecular, genomics, T-cells, antibodies, and interleukins were recorded. It also includes annotation of death caused by CVD after 10 years. Thus, annotation is displayed as the target in our study and is classified into three classes. Class zero represents alive patients, class one is the dead patients due to CVD, and class three displays dead patients due to another disease. We took into account only the class zero and class one, with 2547 patients and 484 patients, respectively. Moreover, we included 20 features in the analysis which are collected, all associated with cardiovascular disease. All features were selected with a feature selection technique,

which is based on the importance of features. These features and their mean values are presented in Table I.

TABLE I. THE DETAILED DATASET ATTRIBUTES DESCRIPTION FOR DATASET (LURIC).

No.	Attributes			
	Features	Type	Mean/Percentage	St. Deviation
1	Age (years)	Numeric	61.98	10.60
2	Sex	Binary	Male=69.2% Female=30.8%	-
3	Weight (kg)	Numeric	79.97	13.69
4	Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	Numeric	192.63	39.18
5	HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	Numeric	38.84	10.88
6	LDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	Numeric	116.85	34.42
7	Cholesterol (mg/dL)	Numeric	208.81	43.96
8	Triglycerides (mg/dL)	Numeric	172.03	115.30
9	LDL Triglycerides (mg/dL)	Numeric	31.28	11.73
10	HDL Triglycerides (mg/dL)	Numeric	15.82	7.03
11	Type II Diabetes Mellitus	Binary	No=83.4% Yes=16.6%	-
12	Urea (mg/dl)	Numeric	39.08	14.96
13	Uric Acid (mg/dl)	Numeric	5.09	1.68
14	Glycosylated hemoglobin (%)	Numeric	6.29	1.23
15	Interleukin-6 (ng/L)	Numeric	12.41	12.70
16	Oxidized LDL	Numeric	74.76	28.30
17	History of arterial hypertension	Binary	No=42.0% Yes=58.0%	-
18	Heart rate	Numeric	68.52	12.27
19	Systolic Blood Pressure	Numeric	140.47	24.60
20	Diastolic Blood Pressure	Numeric	80.94	12.31

C. Data pre-processing

The pre-processing of data has been one of the major steps in our analysis. The techniques applied include cleaning, feature scaling, feature selection, and under sampling for making the balanced dataset.

In our study, we used the down sampling method. This method is applied when the sample size of data is sufficient [22]. We kept all samples in the minority class one and randomly selecting an equal number of samples in the majority class zero. This procedure is finished until the majority and minority class observations are balanced to produce a new balanced 1:1 ratio dataset for further analysis. Eventually, the

analysis was conducted in 484 dead patients and 484 random alive patients.

D. Supervised machine learning algorithms

In the current study, six supervised machine learning classifiers were chosen, including the Random Forest [23], Logistic Regression [24], Support Vector Machine [25], Naïve Bayes [26], Extreme Gradient Boost [27] and Adaptive Boost [28].

E. Performance evaluation metrics

In our analysis, we estimated the performance using standard metrics, namely Accuracy (ACC), Precision, F1-Score, Sensitivity/Recall, and Specificity. Furthermore, the Receiver Operative Characteristic Curve (ROC) and the Area under the ROC curve (AUC) have been employed to compare the performance of each classifier.

III. RESULTS

The results were extracted using the python software package for all classification models. Especially, we utilized the robust library scikit-learn 1.0.2, which is a source with free access to machine learning in python and it provides efficient tools for predictive data analysis. All values of the measurements are shown and compared in Table II. The presented values are the mean values across ten runs.

TABLE II. RESULTS OF THE PEDICTION PERFORMANCE FOR EACH MODEL

Models	Performance Evaluation				
	ACC (%)	Prec*(%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)	Spec^(%)
RF	63.10	76.1	68.4	72.6	76.1
SVM	70.70	73.4	66.8	70.3	73.9
NB	65.21	77.2	48.5	59.4	83.7
LR	72.20	77.5	68.7	72.9	77.0
XGB	72.06	75.4	69.7	72.3	74.3
AdaBoost	64.30	72.3	62.0	68.3	71.7

* Prec=Precision (%), ^Spec=Specificity

Furthermore, the mean values of accuracy are shown in Fig. 2. The results of experiments show that Logistic Regression and Random Forest have 72.20% and 63.10 % respectively, the highest and lowest accuracy of all the classifiers tested. The Logistic Regression classifier is the most suitable model to predict the mortality of CVD in patients with a 10-year history of CVD.

The area under receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) has also been calculated for all applied machine learning algorithms are shown in the Fig. 3. A value of AUC close to 1 signifies that the model has the highest accuracy. Comparing the AUC measurements, we observe that the AUC value of Logistic Regression model is the highest, and the AUC value of Naïve Bayes model is the lowest.

Figure 2. The mean accuracy values for six classifiers.

Figure 3. The mean values of area under receiver operative characteristic curve for six different classifiers.

In addition, the visualization of the results can be achieved using a ROC curve analysis. We plotted the ROC curves for each classifier in an indicative run of the algorithm (Figure 4). Furthermore, we estimated the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve to estimate the efficiency of the applied models. The indicative run of the algorithm shows that Logistic Regression and Support Vector Machine achieved approximately equal AUC values of 0.726 and 0.706, respectively.

Figure 4. Receiver operating characteristic curve of the prediction performance for every classifier in an indicative algorithm run.

IV. CONCLUSION

Monitoring patients with a history of cardiovascular

disease is the most important method for preventing new cases and reducing patient mortality. In this study, the 10-years risk of cardiovascular mortality of patients suffering scheduled for angiography has been predicted utilizing machine learning techniques. Different machine learning models have been applied including Logistic Regression (LR), Random Forest (RF), Naïve Bayes (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Extreme Grading Boosting (XGB) and Adaptive Boosting (AdaBoost). Each algorithm has been tested with various values of parameters to get the highest accuracy before the comparison has been made. The efficiency of each classifier has been evaluated. Among the six different techniques, Logistic Regression outperformed all the others, by having the highest average accuracy (72.20 %) and AUC value (72.97 %). In this paper, our principal goal has been to predict the mortality of CVD using different machine learning techniques in a small dataset and to choose the best predictive computational model comparing them.

There were limitations such as the small number of patients and the absence of optimization techniques in the analysis. We aim to increase the accuracy and validation of these models in the next steps. Finally, a future goal is to assess establish a risk score. In addition, the established Coropredict score will be estimated and compared with its calculated values in the LURIC dataset within the TIMELY study.

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